

ARTICLE

Spatial distribution of an assemblage of an endemic genus of birds: an example from Madagascar

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Email: gianpasquale.chiatante@unipv.it**Abstract**

Knowledge of the distribution and of the realised niche of a species is essential for an understanding of its ecology, especially in the case of poorly known species. To reach this goal, species distribution models (SDMs) can be developed to explain how environmental variables shape the distribution of species. The main aim of this research is to provide new insights concerning the nine species of *Coua*, endemic birds of Madagascar. This study is relevant because ecological studies on *Couas* are uncommon, and although these species are listed as Least Concern by IUCN, some of them are declining. The relationships between each species and the environment, particularly land cover, topography and climate, were investigated through MaxEnt. Next, the amount of niche overlap among species was calculated to investigate whether there is any spatial niche segregation. The results showed that the nine species of *Coua* select many habitat types, especially broadleaved forests, although some species also used mosaics of forests and croplands. Despite the lack of evidence of a larger spatial overlap between different *Coua* species with different habits than between species with similar habits, for many of them, there is overlap, which can mainly be explained by ecological and behavioural differences.

KEYWORDS

Coua, GBIF, Grinnellian niche, Hurlbert's index, MaxEnt, overlap niche, species distribution model

Résumé

La connaissance de la répartition et de la niche réalisée d'une espèce est essentielle pour permettre une bonne compréhension de son écologie, notamment dans les cas où cette même espèce est mal connue. Pour atteindre cet objectif, des modèles de distribution des espèces (SDM) peuvent être développés afin d'expliquer la façon dont les variables environnementales façonnent la répartition des espèces. L'objectif principal de cette recherche est d'apporter de nouvelles connaissances concernant les neuf espèces de *Coua*, oiseaux endémiques de Madagascar. Cette étude est pertinente, car les études écologiques sur les *Couas* sont rares et, bien que ces espèces soient classées dans la catégorie Préoccupation mineure sur la liste rouge de l'UICN, certaines

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d'entre elles sont en déclin. Les relations entre chaque espèce et l'environnement, en particulier l'occupation des sols, la topographie et le climat, ont été étudiées à l'aide de MaxEnt. Le degré de chevauchement des niches entre les espèces a ensuite été calculé afin de déterminer s'il existe une ségrégation spatiale au sein de ces mêmes niches. Les résultats ont montré que les neuf espèces de *Coua* sélectionnaient de nombreux types d'habitats, en particulier les forêts de feuillus. Cependant, certaines espèces utilisaient également des mosaïques de forêts et de terres cultivées. Malgré l'absence de preuves d'un chevauchement spatial plus important entre les espèces de *Coua* ayant des habitudes différentes qu'entre des espèces ayant des habitudes similaires, le chevauchement s'explique principalement par des différences écologiques et comportementales dans la plupart des cas.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of a species' spatial distribution and realised niche is essential for understanding its ecology. One of the first steps in defining the spatial distribution of a species is to explore its spatial niche (also known as Grinnellian niche; Grinnell, 1917), particularly its habitat requirements (Guisan et al., 2017; Soberón, 2007). The basis of species-habitat relationships lies in habitat selection (Cody, 1985; Manly et al., 2002; Morrison et al., 2006), a process by which a species selects resources that are best able to satisfy its life requirements (Hutchinson, 1957). On the other hand, there are also biotic interactions shaping the realised niche of a species, such as competitors and predators, forming the Eltonian niche (Hutchinson, 1957; Soberón, 2007). Similar species often select the same habitat and live sympatrically, even though this could eventually lead to the competitive exclusion of one or more of the competing species (Schoener, 1974). However, among closely related species, extensive niche overlap may be due to niche conservatism (i.e. the degree to which plants and animals retain their niches and related ecological traits through space and time; Peterson, 1999, 2011; Wiens & Graham, 2005). In all these cases, though, many mechanisms permit the coexistence of similar species, such as morphological differentiation (Hutchinson, 1959; Schoener, 1974), trophic niche segregation (Riegert et al., 2011; Tayefeh et al., 2014), microhabitat segregation (Dale & Manceau, 2003; Traba et al., 2013) and temporal separation of their activity patterns (Fedriani et al., 1999; Serafini & Lovari, 1993).

Currently, there is a lack of scientific information on habitat requirements for many species, especially in tropical regions, and the information available is often notional (Beck et al., 2012; Ladle & Whittaker, 2011). In these cases, species distribution models (hereafter SDMs) could be developed in an attempt to explain why a species occurs within a given range, to describe its spatial niche characteristics and to generate predictive maps of its potential distribution (Boyce & McDonald, 1999; Boyce et al., 2002; Guisan & Zimmermann, 2000; Jędrzejewski et al., 2008). Furthermore, SDMs can be used to discover new presence sites (Botero-Delgado et al., 2012; Rhoden et al., 2017) and to plan effective management actions to improve species conservation (Bayliss et al., 2005; Godinho et al., 2013; Robles et al., 2007).

The main aim of this research is to provide new insights concerning Couas (Genus *Coua*), a monophyletic group of endemic birds of Madagascar belonging to the family *Cuculidae* (Erritzøe et al., 2012; Payne, 2005). To this end, the environmental factors (land cover, topography and climate) that drive *Coua* distribution in Madagascar were investigated using SDM, as well as the degree of habitat overlap between them. The relevance of this research lies in the fact that ecological studies about Couas are uncommon and the few that do exist focus mainly on microhabitat selection, foraging and breeding behaviour of only a few species (Chouteau, 2004, 2007; Chouteau & Fenosa, 2008; Chouteau & Pedrono, 2009; Urano et al., 1993). To my knowledge, this is the first attempt to assess the spatial distribution of all *Coua* species by using macroscale environmental predictors. It may also be the first study that shows results about their environmental niche overlap at a macroscale. In general, there is limited knowledge on the potential distribution of these species and to what extent they live in sympatry. Indeed, adaptive radiation in this isolated group of birds has resulted in diversification with species often living in sympatry (Johnson et al., 2000), with spatial distributions more or less overlapping (BirdLife International, 2016, 2017; Electronic Supplemental Material, ESM Table S1). I hypothesised that Couas select different habitat types due to spatial segregation, but that there is also some degree of overlap in habitat selected among ecologically similar species. Indeed, some degree of habitat segregation was expected between two arboreal or two ground species; in contrast, I envisaged that Couas with different habits (i.e. arboreal or ground species) might show some overlap. Moreover, I predicted that habitat overlap between species with different habits (arboreal vs. ground species) would be larger than between species with similar habits (arboreal vs. arboreal or ground vs. ground species).

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Study area

Madagascar is the fourth largest island in the world, covering 587,000 km², located in the Indian Ocean, approximately 400 km off the coast of East Africa (45°42'E, 21°0'S). The altitude ranges from sea level up to 2876 m a.s.l. (Mt. Maromokotro). Madagascar's

climate is generally tropical with a hot rainy season from November to April and a relatively cooler dry season from May to October. The mean annual precipitation varies between 510 and 2640 mm, whereas the mean daily maximum temperature varies from 20 to 31°C (Nassor & Jury, 1997, 1998). Four main climatic zones are recognisable, each corresponding to a specific assemblage of vegetation (Paulian, 1984), that is rainforest along the east coast, dry deciduous forest and grassland in the central highlands, savannah in most of the western plains and spiny forest and desert in the south-west. Mosaics of natural and/or anthropogenic environments (30.6%) cover most of Madagascar's landscape. Grasslands make up 29% of its surface, followed by forests (20%, of which 10.7% are broadleaved deciduous and 9.1% are broadleaved evergreen or semi-deciduous forests), shrublands (19.4%) and mangroves (0.2%) (ESM Figure S1).

2.2 | Study species

The genus *Coua* (family Cuculidae) includes nine extant species that have no close affinity with other genera within their family (Erritzøe et al., 2012; Payne, 2005). There are three arboreal species (Blue Coua *C. caerulea*, Crested Coua *C. cristata* and Verreaux's Coua *C. verreauxi*) and six ground species (Coquerel's Coua *C. coquereli*, Running Coua *C. cursor*, Giant Coua *C. gigas*, Red-fronted Coua *C. reynaudii*, Red-capped Coua *C. ruficeps* and Red-breasted Coua *C. serriana*). Their diet consists mainly of arthropods, and little is known about their breeding biology (del Hoyo et al., 1997; Erritzøe et al., 2012; Payne, 2005). All the species are listed as Least Concern by IUCN because of their stable populations, even though it is suspected that Crested and Verreaux's Couas are in decline owing to habitat loss, degradation and hunting pressure (BirdLife International, 2016, 2017). One species is considered extinct, the Snail-eating Coua (*C. delalandei*), a ground snail-eating specialist on Île Sainte Marie (northeast of Madagascar), last seen around 1835 during a time of deforestation. Hunting, along with the introduction of rats that depleted the food source (terrestrial snails), may have been the factor in its extinction (del Hoyo et al., 1997; Erritzøe et al., 2012; Payne, 2005).

2.3 | Species dataset

Distributional data of the nine Coua species were downloaded from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) Data Portal (<http://www.gbif.org/>). This facility has become a gateway to the largest biological data repositories around the world (e.g. eBird, Xeno-canto) by making data sets held by many institutions accessible. It has been used widely for obtaining data about the spatial distribution of many species (Franklin & Miller, 2009; Ladle & Whittaker, 2011) and to perform SDM both for plant and for animal species (Bystrakova et al., 2012; Fourcade et al., 2014; Rödder, 2009; Syfert et al., 2013). To better relate species occurrence with

the current environment, only data collected after 2000 were used in the analyses. Moreover, to improve data quality, observations with missing or false locality coordinates were excluded, as well as records falling outside the known species range (Beck et al., 2014; Chapman, 2005; Rödder & Lötters, 2009). Besides, when required, marginal records, that is those isolated and located at the boundaries of the species range, were not used, as such records can lead to the overestimation of niches and of geographically suitable areas (Soley-Guardia et al., 2016).

2.4 | Environmental predictors

The spatial distribution of the Couas was assessed using variables related to land cover, topography and climate (Table 1). Data concerning the land cover were acquired from the Global Land Cover (GLC2000), a database with a regionally optimised land cover legend, based mainly on daily data from the VEGETATION sensor onboard SPOT 4 (Bartholomé & Belward, 2005). Moreover, to better characterise the vegetation, the study included all the four ecoregions of Madagascar (mangrove, moist forest, dry forest and spiny forest), which were defined based on climatic and vegetation criteria (Vieilledent et al., 2016, 2017). Also, a raster grid describing the density of rivers (m/km²) was generated as some species live in gallery forests and near rivers (del Hoyo et al., 1997; Erritzøe et al., 2012; Payne, 2005). Topographical variables were derived from the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of Madagascar with a spatial resolution of 1 km. In particular, besides altitude and slope, the circular variable aspect was transformed into a linear north-south gradient (northness) and an east-west gradient (eastness), by cosine and sine transformations, respectively (Bueno et al., 2009; Kumar et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2010). Finally, I used five bioclimatic variables at a spatial resolution of 30 s (~1 km²) by WorldClim 2.1 (available at www.worldclim.org), a database of high spatial resolution global weather and climate data, frequently used to compute SDMs (Fick & Hijmans, 2017). All the variables were resampled to a spatial resolution of 1 × 1 km (the lowest spatial resolution of environmental data), and the variance inflation factor (VIF) was computed (Table 1) with a threshold of 3 to test variable collinearity (Fox & Monette, 1992; Zuur et al., 2010). Due to collinearity (see also ESM Table S2), two bioclimatic variables (BIO12 annual precipitation and BIO17 precipitation of the driest quarter) were not used. The spatial analyses were computed by QuantumGIS v2.14.12 and by the software R v3.4.3 and the related packages *raster* (Hijmans et al., 2014), *sp* (Pebesma & Bivand, 2011) and *usdm* (Naimi, 2017).

2.5 | Species distribution modelling

In this study, SDMs were built individually for each Coua by the MaxEnt algorithm (Phillips et al., 2006), a machine learning method that applies the principle of maximum entropy to predict the potential distribution of species from presence-only data (Elith et al., 2011;

TABLE 1 Environmental variables used to define the spatial distribution of nine species of *Coua* in Madagascar by MaxEnt

Environmental variable	Abbreviation	Mean \pm SD	VIF
Land cover (% cover)			
Mosaic of forest and croplands	GLC32	8.6 \pm 0.029	2.79 (8.64)
Closed broadleaved evergreen and/or semi-deciduous forest	GLC41	7.5 \pm 0.023	1.80 (7.89)
Closed broadleaved deciduous forest	GLC50	10.7 \pm 0.023	1.29 (5.74)
Mosaic of grassland and forest or shrubland	GLC120	16.0 \pm 0.020	1.55 (4.76)
Closed to open shrubland	GLC130	10.1 \pm 0.016	1.97 (4.13)
Closed to open broadleaved deciduous shrubland	GLC134	8.7 \pm 0.016	1.94 (3.80)
Closed grassland	GLC141	28.3 \pm 0.041	2.25 (14.80)
Ecoregions			
mangrove	MA	0.5%	-
moist forest	MO	34.8%	
dry forest	DR	55.5%	
spiny forest	SP	9.2%	
River density (m/km ²)		88 \pm 0.150	1.02 (1.04)
Topography			
Altitude (m)		540 \pm 0.588	1.53 (20.89)
Slope (°)		1.99 \pm 0.003	1.27 (1.29)
Northness		0.02 \pm 0.001	1.02 (1.03)
Eastness		-0.04 \pm 0.001	1.06 (1.05)
Climate			
Annual mean temperature (°C)	BIO1	22.9 \pm 0.004	1.52 (1.82)
Annual precipitation (mm)	BIO12	1393 \pm 0.708	- (89.92)
Precipitation seasonality (coefficient of variation)	BIO15	99.7 \pm 0.031	1.69 (16.09)
Precipitation of the wettest quarter (mm)	BIO16	821 \pm 0.311	1.31 (46.85)
Precipitation of the driest quarter (mm)	BIO17	67 \pm 0.120	- (27.62)

Note: The variance inflation factor (VIF) is shown (between brackets the VIF before the exclusion of collinear variables from the analyses).

Phillips & Dudík, 2008). The use of presence-only data is useful because in many cases it is difficult to assess the absence of a species, especially when the survey design does not involve repeated visits to the study sites. At least three to five surveys should be performed to determine with reasonable error the absence of a species at a site, especially in habitats with lower detection probabilities such as forests (Buckland et al., 1993; MacKenzie et al., 2006; Tyre et al., 2003). In other cases, as for most regions, systematic biological survey data tend to be sparse and/or limited in coverage, being available only in the form of records in herbaria, museum specimens and online databases (e.g. GBIF). For this huge source of data, SDMs are essential for modelling presence-only data (Elith et al., 2006, 2011). In addition, MaxEnt outperforms most alternative methods (Elith et al., 2006) and is particularly efficient for small sample sizes (Pearson et al., 2006; Wisz et al., 2008). One fundamental assumption of MaxEnt models is that the entire area of interest has been randomly sampled (Phillips et al., 2009). Considering the source of data used in this study, it is likely that the occurrence records are spatially biased towards better-surveyed areas. It is largely known that spatial bias may lead to inaccurate models; thus, some approaches have been developed to correct this bias (Kramer-Schadt et al., 2013; Phillips

et al., 2009; Stolar & Nielsen, 2015). In this research, a sample bias file was created for each species, which is a sampling probability surface built by a Gaussian kernel density map of the occurrence locations (ESM Figure S2). These maps were used to select spatially weighted species-specific background points (Clements et al., 2012; Fourcade et al., 2014; Vergara et al., 2016). For each species, three replicates with cross-validation were performed and the final model presented is computed as the average of the three models (McCune, 2016; Zhao et al., 2017). MaxEnt was run with only linear and quadratic features to ensure more ecologically realistic response curves (Bateman et al., 2012, 2016) using 10,000 background points, and other parameters set to default (maximum number of iterations = 5000; convergence threshold = 10^{-5}) (Elith et al., 2011; Phillips & Dudík, 2008). Duplicate occurrence points in the same grid cell were removed so that only one point per grid cell was retained to reduce bias related to spatial correlation (Chou et al., 2020; Petrovan et al., 2020). To obtain the most parsimonious model, the variables were retained by the corrected Akaike information criterion (AIC_c) (Akaike, 1973; Burnham & Anderson, 2002; Warren & Seifert, 2011). First, a full model was generated, then omitting the variables with the lowest permutation importance (Meyer et al., 2014), which is a

criterion to measure the contribution which each variable makes to the full model (Elith et al., 2011). Finally, the model with the lowest AIC_c was considered the best (Burnham & Anderson, 2002; Warren & Seifert, 2011). The regularisation multiplier parameter, for which default regularisation values may lead to overfitted models (Anderson & Gonzalez Jr., 2011; Cao et al., 2013; Radosavljevic & Anderson, 2014), was set manually. To reduce the complexity of the model, and thus the likelihood of over-parameterisation, as well as the risk of model overfitting, models with different values for the regularisation multiplier (default setting 0.01, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 5.0) were calibrated, after which AIC_c values were used to select the most parsimonious models (Delgado-Jaramillo et al., 2020; Rodríguez-Ruiz et al., 2019). The model accuracy was tested through omission error rates, calculated using the fixed sensitivity threshold equal to 0.95, meaning that 95% of training occurrence localities were included in the prediction (Peterson et al., 2011). Model performance was assessed using the omission error rates so that models with values $\leq 5\%$ were considered to perform well (Anderson et al., 2003). This threshold was used also to reclassify the logistic suitability maps into binary maps of suitable/unsuitable areas (Peterson et al., 2011). Although this discretisation may lose some information (Guillera-Aroita et al., 2015), in conservation and environmental management practice, presenting the information as suitable/unsuitable areas may be more practical than as probability or suitability (Araújo et al., 2004, 2006).

Finally, the niche overlap of the Couas whose distributions overlapped at least by 10% of their extent (as defined by BirdLife International, 2016, 2017; ESM Table S1) was calculated by Hurlbert's index, which allows for the possibility that resources vary in abundance (Krebs, 1999). However, for completeness, this index was also calculated for Couas whose distributions do not overlap. This index was calculated as follows:

$$L = \sum_i^n \left(\frac{p_{ij}p_{ik}}{a_i} \right)$$

where L is the Hurlbert's measure of niche overlap between species j and k ; p_{ij} is the proportion of resource i out of the total resources used by species j ; p_{ik} is the proportion of resource i out of the total resources used by species k ; and a_i is the proportional amount of resource i

($\sum a_i = 1.0$). This index is 1.0 when both species used each resource in proportion to its availability (no selection is evident), 0 when the two species did not share resources and >1.0 when the two species both use some resource beyond its availability and the requirements of the two species tend to coincide. In this study, the resources were represented by land cover variables (see Table 1); thus, values greater than 1.0 occurred when two species use the same habitat to a greater extent than its proportional availability, indicating their convergence on a common habitat requirement (Krebs, 1999; Steffan-Dewenter & Tschardt, 2000). The reliability of this index was tested by resampling the data 1000 times with the bootstrap method and calculating the mean values and 95% confidence intervals (Legendre & Legendre, 1998). Finally, a comparison was performed of Hurlbert's index between species with different habits (arboreal vs. ground species) and between species with similar habits (arboreal vs. arboreal or ground vs. ground) using the permutation test for one-way analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) with 9999 randomisations.

The statistical analyses were carried out by the software R 3.4.3 (R Core Team, 2019) and the packages *dismo* (Hijmans et al., 2011), *ENMeval* (Muscarella et al., 2017) and *PresenceAbsence* (Freeman, 2012).

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Couas' habitat correlates

Removing duplicates and marginal records (only one for Red-capped Coua at the southern margin of its range), 18 to 99 occurrences were retained for each species since 2000 (Table 2). The distribution of Couas was related mainly to habitat types, with climate and topography being of lesser importance (Figures 1-2; ESM Table S3). For example, the Blue Coua was related mainly to the absence of mosaics of forests and croplands; moreover, low mean annual temperature favoured this species' occurrence. The distribution of the Coquerel's Coua was linked to dry forests and the absence of mosaics of grasslands and forests/shrublands. Giant Coua selected mainly closed broadleaved deciduous forests, whereas the Crested Coua used mosaics of forests and croplands, avoiding deciduous shrublands. The distribution of the Running Coua was affected mainly by low precipitation and slope, which showed a

TABLE 2 MaxEnt model attributes: number of presence sites (N) (between brackets is the number of occurrences used for testing), β regularization multiplier (β -reg), omission error rate (OE), 0.95 sensitivity threshold (SENS_0.95) and range predicted in Madagascar by the binary map (Range)

Species	N	β -reg	OE	SENS_0.95	Range
Blue Coua <i>C. caerulea</i>	99 (33)	0.5	0.03	0.08	27.3%
Coquerel's Coua <i>C. coquereli</i>	27 (9)	0.1	0.04	0.13	24.2%
Crested Coua <i>C. cristata</i>	46 (15)	0.01	0.04	0.19	31.6%
Running Coua <i>C. cursor</i>	23 (8)	0.1	0.04	0.20	6.5%
Giant Coua <i>C. gigas</i>	27 (9)	0.01	0.00	0.08	14.5%
Red-fronted Coua <i>C. reynaudii</i>	72 (24)	0.01	0.04	0.08	17.5%
Red-capped Coua <i>C. ruficeps</i>	18 (6)	0.01	0.00	0.02	19.6%
Red-breasted Coua <i>C. serriana</i>	25 (8)	0.01	0.04	0.24	11.7%
Verreaux's Coua <i>C. verreauxi</i>	28 (9)	0.01	0.04	0.09	2.9%

FIGURE 1 Response curves of the environmental variables. Response curves of the most influential environmental variables on Coua distribution in Madagascar (a: *C. caerulea*, b-c: *C. coquereli*, d-e: *C. cristata*, f-g: *C. cursor*, h: *C. gigas*, i: *C. reynaudii*, j: *C. ruficeps*, k-m: *C. serriana*, n: *C. verreauxi*). The y-axis shows the environmental suitability (0 unsuitable, 1 suitable). For variable abbreviations, see Table 1

FIGURE 2 Permutation importance of the environmental variables. Permutation importance of the environmental variables selected in the best models explaining Cooua distribution in Madagascar. Species abbreviations: *Ccae* Blue Cooua, *Ccoq* Coquerel's Cooua, *Ccri* Crested Cooua, *Ccur* Running Cooua, *Cgig* Giant Cooua, *Crey* Red-fronted Cooua, *Cruf* Red-capped Cooua, *Cser* Red-breasted Cooua, *Cver* Verreaux's Cooua

negative effect. Two species, the Red-fronted and the Red-capped Cooua, inhabited areas with low mean annual temperature. The Red-breasted Cooua used mosaics of forests and croplands, as well as the high cover of broadleaved deciduous forests. Finally, Verreaux's Cooua was negatively affected by broadleaved deciduous forests. The less important variables (ESM Figures S3-S11) are made up almost exclusively of habitats that negatively affected the species' occurrence, such as closed to open shrublands, closed to open broadleaved deciduous shrublands and the density of rivers. The SDMs for all the species showed an omission error rate of below 5% and can therefore be considered good enough (Table 2). The Running Cooua and Verreaux's Cooua were the species with the smallest predicted distribution, whereas the Blue, Coquerel's and Crested Coouas had the largest (Table 2; Figures 3-4).

3.2 | Environmental niche overlap among Coouas

There were 18 species pairs whose ranges overlapped (ESM Table S1). The Hurlbert's index showed six pairs of Cooua species with strong niche overlap (Table 3): Blue and Red-fronted, Blue and Red-breasted, Coquerel's and Crested, Coquerel's and Red-capped, Crested and Red-capped, and Red-fronted and Red-breasted. At the same time, there was a moderate degree of overlap between the niches of eight species, whereas between six there was no overlap (Table 3). There was only a moderate macrohabitat niche overlap

between two allopatric species, the Red-fronted and the Red-capped (ESM Table S4). Furthermore, there were no significant differences in Hurlbert's Index between species with different and similar habits (PERMANOVA, $F_{1,16} = 0.016$, $p = .908$). Among them, there was only one pair of arboreal Coouas, but no significant results were obtained even when only ground species were tested (PERMANOVA, $F_{1,15} = 0.004$, $p = .949$) (ESM Figure S12).

4 | DISCUSSION

The first part of this study was an investigation of the spatial distribution of Coouas using SDM, an approach never previously employed for this genus. Overall, the MaxEnt models computed show adequate performance, but for species with small sample size (e.g. *C. ruficeps*), results should be considered with caution (Pearson et al., 2006; Wisz et al., 2008). Uncertainties in these models could also be related to other issues. First, there may be some sources of error in the GBIF database, such as wrong species names or localities (Beck et al., 2014; Chapman, 2005), potentially leading to erroneous evaluations of species ecology and inaccurate SDMs (Beck et al., 2014). Besides, especially for species with a small sample size, over-parameterization could also lead to biased results. Indeed, fitting a model with too many predictors may result in modelling spurious relationships (Warren & Seifert, 2011) and underprediction (Anderson & Gonzalez Jr., 2011; Rodda et al., 2011). Moreover, a bias may occur in relation to

FIGURE 3 Spatial distribution models of Couas in Madagascar (a *C. caerulea*, b *C. coquereli*, c *C. cristata*, d *C. cursor*, e *C. gigas*, f *C. reynaudii*, g *C. ruficeps*, h *C. serriana*, i *C. verreauxi*). Suitability increase passing from red (low suitability) to blue (high suitability). The black dots represent the species occurrence locations

FIGURE 4 Binary maps of the spatial distribution of Coua in Madagascar. The reclassified suitable/unsuitable maps of the Coua species in Madagascar (a *C. caerulea*, b *C. coquereli*, c *C. cristata*, d *C. cursor*, e *C. gigas*, f *C. reynaudii*, g *C. ruficeps*, h *C. serriana*, i *C. verreauxi*). Suitable areas are represented in green; the red dots represent the species occurrence locations, whereas the IUCN species distributions are shown in yellow

TABLE 3 Hurlbert's index of niche overlaps among Couas that have at least 10% of their distributions overlapping. In bold the pairs with the strongest overlap, and in italics the pairs without niche overlap

Species	Habits	HI	SE	LCI	UCI
Blue Coua vs Crested Coua	A vs A	1.146	0.003	1.141	1.152
Blue Coua vs Red-fronted Coua	A vs G	4.340	0.003	4.334	4.346
<i>Blue Coua vs Red-capped Coua</i>	<i>A vs G</i>	<i>0.882</i>	<i>0.001</i>	<i>0.879</i>	<i>0.884</i>
Blue Coua vs Red-breasted Coua	A vs G	4.374	0.005	4.365	4.383
Coquerel's Coua vs Crested Coua	G vs A	3.076	0.004	3.067	3.084
<i>Coquerel's Coua vs Running Coua</i>	<i>G vs G</i>	<i>0.411</i>	<i>0.001</i>	<i>0.409</i>	<i>0.412</i>
Coquerel's Coua vs Giant Coua	G vs G	1.871	0.003	1.865	1.876
Coquerel's Coua vs Red-capped Coua	G vs G	3.427	0.005	3.418	3.437
<i>Coquerel's Coua vs Verreaux's Coua</i>	<i>G vs A</i>	<i>0.363</i>	<i>0.001</i>	<i>0.361</i>	<i>0.365</i>
Crested Coua vs Giant Coua	A vs G	1.787	0.003	1.781	1.794
Crested Coua vs Red-fronted Coua	A vs G	1.206	0.003	1.200	1.211
Crested Coua vs Red-capped Coua	A vs G	3.438	0.005	3.428	3.449
<i>Crested Coua vs Red-breasted Coua</i>	<i>A vs G</i>	<i>0.871</i>	<i>0.003</i>	<i>0.865</i>	<i>0.878</i>
<i>Running Coua vs Giant Coua</i>	<i>G vs G</i>	<i>0.760</i>	<i>0.001</i>	<i>0.758</i>	<i>0.761</i>
Running Coua vs Verreaux's Coua	G vs A	1.288	0.001	1.286	1.290
Giant Coua vs Red-capped Coua	G vs G	1.949	0.004	1.942	1.957
<i>Giant Coua vs Verreaux's Coua</i>	<i>G vs A</i>	<i>0.851</i>	<i>0.001</i>	<i>0.848</i>	<i>0.854</i>
Red-fronted Coua vs Red-breasted Coua	G vs G	4.128	0.005	4.118	4.137

Note: The index (HI) is shown with standard error (SE) and 95% confidence interval (lower interval LCI, upper interval UCI). Also, species habits are shown (A = arboreal species, G = ground species).

the spatial resolution used to measure the environmental variables. Indeed, in the analyses carried out in this research, I measured variables in a 1 × 1 km grid, which could be appropriate for some species though not for others. Therefore, it is likely that the environmental factors shaping the species' occurrence operate at a different resolution than the one used in this study, at least for some species. Indeed, some studies underline that environmental factors act at many different spatial scales (Chiatante et al., 2019; Fischer & Lindenmayer, 2007; Jackson & Fahrig, 2015). Furthermore, in some cases using isolated marginal records can lead to substantial overestimations of niches and, consequently, of geographically suitable areas (Soley-Guardia et al., 2016). In this research, for some species, the suitability map resulted in a wider (Crested, Giant and Red-capped Couas) or in a more restricted distribution (Blue, Coquerel's, Red-fronted and Red-breasted Couas) than their known ranges, which does not mean necessarily that the predictions are wrong but more likely that they are incomplete. In fact, some important predictor variables are probably missing from the models (such as microhabitat variables or biological interactions) and the covariates used do not fully explain the spatial distribution of each species. Indeed, even though when projecting models in space, the full realised niche should be captured (Guisan et al., 2017; Thuiller et al., 2004), this rarely happens because usually only the quantified realised niche is projected, based on field observations (Araújo & Guisan, 2006; Soberón, 2007). Consequently, a model built with data covering only a limited part of a species' niche (as in this research due to the species data set used) may introduce errors when projected (Guisan et al., 2017; Thuiller et al., 2004).

The results showed that two species, the Giant and the Red-breasted, use broadleaved evergreen or semi-deciduous forests, according to current knowledge (Chouteau et al., 2004; Erritzøe et al., 2012; Goodman et al., 1997; Payne, 2005). The negative effect of this forest type on Verreaux's Coua is linked to the fact that it is a forest type growing from north to south along the narrow and steep eastern escarpment of the Central Highlands, outside the range of this species. Coquerel's Coua selected dry forests, as is already known (Chouteau et al., 2004; Erritzøe et al., 2012), avoiding mosaics of forests, grasslands and croplands, similarly to Blue Coua. As a matter of fact, these two species both selected mainly primary forests (Erritzøe et al., 2012; Payne, 2005). Contrarily, both the Crested and the Red-breasted Couas selected mosaics of forests and croplands. Indeed, these species, despite being forest birds, also used open areas, such as savannah and brushlands, especially the latter (Erritzøe et al., 2012; Payne, 2005). Furthermore, the suitability of Madagascar for many species is driven by the absence of shrublands, which has also been recorded by other researchers (Erritzøe et al., 2012; Payne, 2005). Concerning climate, the most important variable seems to be mean annual temperature, negatively affecting the Blue, the Red-fronted and the Red-capped Couas.

The second aim of this study was to define the degree of spatial overlap between Couas, particularly in their chosen habitat, on the basis of the results obtained using the SDMs. Spatial overlap was to be expected between species with different ecological habits, that is arboreal vs ground species, in contrast to two arboreal species or two ground species. Even though no general pattern emerged from

the statistical analyses, the results showed that there are six species pairs with strong spatial overlap. In four cases, this spatial overlap, as expected, could be explained by different habits, with arboreal species (in this case, Blue and Crested Couas) coexisting with ground species (Red-fronted and Red-breasted Couas, and Coquerel's and Red-capped Couas, respectively). On the other hand, between two ground species (Coquerel's and Red-capped Coua), there was spatial overlap where they select different microhabitats. Indeed, Coquerel's Coua appears to be linked to habitats with tall trees and large numbers of lianas and stems (Chouteau et al., 2004), whereas the Red-capped Coua is absent from habitats with large trees and forages more often where understorey vegetation is not well developed (such as burned areas or logged forests) (Chouteau, 2007; Chouteau & Fenosa, 2008; Chouteau et al., 2004; Urano et al., 1993). Therefore, as expected, the different foraging strategies of ecologically similar species ensure they can coexist. Similarly, another pair of ground species (Coquerel's and Giant Coua) showed a moderate spatial overlap, even though they had different foraging behaviours. Indeed, the Coquerel's selects foraging sites with more stems, denser understorey and more litter than the Giant (Chouteau, 2004, 2006). Contrary to expectations, three pairs of species shared the same habitat and were ecologically similar. Two arboreal species, Blue and Crested Couas, showed some unexpected overlap, even though their sympatric area is restricted to the west coast of Madagascar and, additionally, the first is restricted to deciduous forests, littoral forests and mangroves, unlike the latter (Erritzø et al., 2012; Payne, 2005). Besides, spatial overlap was also found between two pairs of ground species, Red-fronted vs Red-breasted and Giant vs Red-capped. However, microhabitat segregation, which has never been investigated, may exist between them due to differences in their life histories (i.e. home ranges of different sizes, different heights and nesting places) (Chouteau, 2003).

In conclusion, the nine species of Couas select many habitat types, especially broadleaved forests, even though some species also used mosaics of forests and croplands. Despite the lack of evidence of larger niche overlap between Couas with different habits than between species with similar habits, for many of them there is some niche overlap. Likely, they may coexist because of both microhabitat segregation and abundance of resources, also considering their different feeding or breeding habits. Future investigations will attempt to collect more data about the distribution of Couas, so as to improve the models used thus far. In addition, the role of microhabitat and biotic interactions affecting species distribution will be crucial for a better understanding of the realised niche among Couas.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial or not-for-profit sectors. Open access funding provided by Università degli Studi di Pavia within the CRUI-CARE Agreement. I would like to warmly thank Caterina Cullati for her helpful comments on the first draft of the manuscript. I would like to thank Anthony Green and Pamela Denmon (AFO Editorial Assistance Program) for English revision.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares that he has no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analysed in this study. However, all data used are downloadable from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) Data Portal (<http://www.gbif.org/>).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found online in the Supporting Information section.

How to cite this article: Chiatante, G. (2022). Spatial distribution of an assemblage of an endemic genus of birds: an example from Madagascar. *Afr J Ecol*, 60, 13–26. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aje.12917>